

The Development of a Large Three-Axis Magnetic Field Susceptibility Test (L-TAMFST) System

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Abstract: This paper describes the development and operation of the large three-axis magnetic field susceptibility test fixture (L-TAMFST) at the Naval Undersea Warfare Center (NUWC). L-TAMFST is a multi-axis Helmholtz coil test fixture that is used to perform magnetic field susceptibility testing on equipment racks, as large as 6 ft x 2 ft x 2 ft, in accordance with DOD-STD-1399 Section 070. The L-TAMFST fixture is capable of generating DC fields in excess of 20 Oersted directed at virtually any angle. The generated fields can be either uniform or gradient, in order to subject the test article to realistic conditions. Specifically, this paper addresses the overall hardware, the control system, analytical models (used for development purposes), and experimental data.

Introduction

The magnetic field susceptibility of equipment is becoming increasingly important as electronic equipment is used more frequently in military and industrial applications where strong fields may be present (e.g. ships, factories, power plants, etc.). Equipment such as computer monitors are particularly susceptible to relatively small magnetic fields. The presence of such fields can distort images, skew the display, and alter the display colors. In some cases, the monitors may suffer short and/or long term damage. Therefore, it is important to test subject the equipment, which may perform critical functions, to simulated magnetic field environments prior to the actual installation.

The L-TAMFST system is an outgrowth of the smaller TAMFST system developed at NUWC for testing single computer monitors. [1] L-TAMFST is designed to simplify the magnetic field susceptibility testing of equipment racks. The system is capable of generating a uniform DC field on the order of 20 Oersted while dynamically rotating the field around any of the three axes. The combination of these fields emulate the conditions found in actual operating environments. This paper describes the design of the L-TAMFST system.

Hardware

The overall hardware configuration for the L-TAMFST system is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. L-TAMFST Hardware Configuration

The test fixture consists of nine coils that are independently controlled. A computer controls the current supplied to each coil. This enables the operator to precisely control the field profiles including, magnitude, gradient, and direction.

The control system for the L-TAMFST system was developed using a commercially available data acquisition system (DAS). The DAS runs on a Macintosh computer, but could just as well be operated from a PC or workstation. The DAS provides the interactivity between the user and the system. A screen snap shot of the user interface is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. L-TAMFST Control Panel

The L-TAMFST user interface allows the operator to specify the field levels, field direction, rotation rate, and gradient. The user interface also displays the current for each coil.

The user also has the ability to create and store test scenarios (e.g., gradient profiles, rotation patterns, etc.) that can be run during an experiment. This allows the operator to monitor the equipment under test for signs of degradation.

The DAS is comprised of a series of software modules were created that provide the user interface, derive the coil currents, and provide the instrumentation control. The software is programmed to send information via a IEEE-488 bus to the power supplies.

The currents required to generate a specific field profile are computed based upon a coil factor that establishes a relation between the applied coil current and the magnetic field produced by the coil. The factors for each coil are used to create a system of linear equations which are solved for a specified field level and direction, to obtain the current (including polarity) for each coil. The rotating fields, where the field rotates about an axis, is generated by time sequencing the currents applied to two axes at a time. This produces a rotation about the third axis. This information is passed to the power supplies via an IEEE-488 bus.

L-TAMFST utilizes nine DC power supplies ranging in power from 1 kW to 5 kW. A separate supply is used to drive each coil. The power supplies operate in the constant current mode, that is the supply delivers the required current. The output of the power supplies are sent to a bank of tri-state relays. As with the power supplies, there is one relay per coil.

The relays serve a dual purpose. First, they provide a safety mechanism for quickly shutting off the current from the supplies. Secondly, since they operate in a tri-state mode, they are capable of reversing the polarity of the current. This important for changing the direction of the fields. The test fixture consists of nine coils that are independently controlled. There are two pairs of large coils in the axial (X), transverse (Y) directions and a vertical stack of five coils for the vertical (Z) direction as illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3. L-TAMFST Coils

The large coils measure approximately 6 ft in diameter while the smaller vertical coils have a diameter of 4 ft. This provides a uniform test volume which is approximately 6 ft x 2 ft x 2ft.

Each coil has approximately 100 turns of 1/4"x1/4" bar conductors. The DC resistance of each coil is approximately 0.5 ohms. The 6 ft coils are mounted on individual bases that allow the coils to be moved for storage purposes. The coils in the center stack are supported by a series of wooden dowels. The dowels keep the stack centered and allow the stack to be collapsed for storage.

Analytical Models

The magnetic field generated by the Helmholtz coils can be modeled using several different techniques. One closed form solution for the magnetic field produced by a single axis Helmholtz coil system is computed as [2]

$$B_z = \frac{\mu_0 N I a^2}{2} \left(\frac{1}{(z^2 + a^2)^{3/2}} + \frac{1}{((z^2 - d^2) + a^2)^{3/2}} \right)$$

where,

- I = current
- N = number of turns
- d = coil separation
- a = coil radius
- z = distance along z axis

The uniformity of the field can be computed by iterating the above equation over the distance Z. Figure 4 illustrates the uniformity of the field for coil diameter of 2 meters and a separation of 1 meter.

Figure 4. Uniformity of Helmholtz Coil Field

This figure illustrates that the field is uniform for the center half of the volume enclosed by the coils.

The Helmholtz coil equation can be factored and vectorized to estimate the contributions produced by each of the

individual coils in a multiple coil system. The effects of changing the drive currents to the individual coils can also be predicted.

Sample Test Results

Magnetic field susceptibility testing is often required for shipboard equipment. In most cases, DOD-STD-1399 Section 070 testing is specified. Equipment tested to this specification is generally exposed to the magnetic field from the three orthogonal directions. The advantage of a system such as L-TAMFST, is that the unit can be to more real world conditions where the magnetic fields can arrive from virtually any direction.

Computer monitors are particularly susceptible to the effects of magnetic fields. The distortion caused by the magnetic fields can vary significantly depending on direction and characterization of the magnetic field. An example of the variation is illustrated in the following figures. Figure 5 shows a monitor subjected to a vertical field.

Figure 5. Field Applied in Vertical Direction

The illustrations shows some minor discoloration along the edges of the screen and in the center. The regions of color change have been highlighted. The color codes are as follows: P = purple, Y = yellow, G = green. The test screen is normally red. Figure 6 shows the same monitor with the field applied at 65 degrees from the vertical position towards the rear of the monitor).

Figure 6. Field Applied 65 deg From Vertical

This photo shows severe discoloration of the screen. The screen is divided into approximately six areas of vastly different colors. Thus, the same field level produced drastically different effects depending on the angle of incidence. Since the automated test setup was able to rapidly apply the field at all angles, a potential susceptibility was noted which would have gone undetected by a traditional DOD-STD-1399 test.

Conclusion

An automated, multi-axis Helmholtz coil test fixture provides a suitable means for simulating the shipboard magnetic environment. The use of the automated test system provides a good means of determining whether or not electronic equipment will function properly aboard Navy ships.

References

- [1] Schade, N. "Description and Operations Manual for the Three-Axis Magnetic Field Susceptibility Test (TAMFST) System", Naval Undersea Warfare Center, TM-921147, April 1993.
- [2] Fogiel, M., *The Electromagnetics Problem Solver*, Research and Education Association, New York, 1983.

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